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EFFECT OF POLYMERS AND GAS FORMING AGENTS ON GASTRO RETENTIVE FLOATING TABLETS OF ATORVASTATIN CALCIUM

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ABSTRACT

Atorvastatin Calcium is a lipid lowering drug. It is a HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor used in the treatment of hyper lipidaemia. It has a oral bioavailability of less than 12% Floating matrix tablets are designed to prolong the gastric residence time after oral administration, at a particular site and controlling the release of drug, especially useful for achieving controlled plasma level as well as improving bioavailability. With this objective, floating dosage form containing Atorvastatin Calcium as drug was designed. Tablets containing hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC), drug and different additives were compressed using wet granulation. The study shows that tablet composition has great influence on the floating properties and drug release. Incorporation of gas-generating agent together with polymer improved drug release, besides optimal floating (floating lag time ~30 s; total floating time >12 h). The drug release was sufficiently sustained (more than 11h) and non-Fickian as well as zero-order was confirmed.

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INTRODUCTION

Most of the orally administered dosage forms have several physiological limitations, such as GI transit time, incomplete drug absorption due to incomplete release of drug from the devices and too short residence time of the dosage forms in the absorption region of GI tract. To overcome these limitations many attempts have been made by scientists by designing various drug delivery systems.

Among these systems, Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) is one of the approaches which remain buoyant due to their lower density than that of the GI and intestinal fluids. Both single and multiple unit systems have been developed^{1,2} prolonged gastro retention of the therapeutic moiety may offer numerous advantages, including improvement of bioavailability, therapeutic efficiency and possible reduction of dose^{3,4,5}. It has been reported that prolonged local availability of antibacterial agents may augment their effectiveness in treating H. Pylori infections⁶.

FDDS have a bulk density lower than gastric fluid and thus remains buoyant in stomach for prolonged period of time without affecting gastric emptying time. They are also referred to as hydro dynamically balanced systems (HBS) as they are able to maintain their low density. Based on mechanisms of floating, two different technologies i.e., Effervescent FDDS and Non-effervescent FDDS were attempted to release drug. In case of effervescent systems, when they reach the stomach CO₂ is liberated by the acidity of gastric content and is entrapped in jellified hydro colloid. When the liberated gas is expelled from the dosage form it creates pores through which water can easily pass and helps in wetting of the polymers.

The CO₂ generated compounds like sodium bicarbonate, calcium carbonate; citric acid/tartaric acid mixtures can be used⁷⁻¹⁰. Non-effervescent floating dosage forms use a gel forming or swellable cellulose type of hydrocolloids, polysaccharides, and matrix-forming polymers like polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polymethacrylate, and polystyrene. The

formulation method includes a simple approach of thoroughly mixing the drug and the gel-forming hydrocolloid. After oral administration this dosage form swells in contact with gastric fluids and attains a bulk density of less than 1. The air entrapped within the swollen matrix imparts buoyancy to the dosage form. Atorvastatin calcium is a HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor used in the treatment of hyperlipidaemia. It has an oral bioavailability of less than 12%. It also undergoes high first pass metabolism. It is highly soluble in acidic pH and absorbed more in the upper part of the GIT. In order to improve the absorption and its oral bioavailability, we have attempted to formulate a floating drug delivery systems using Atorvastatin calcium as the model drug with HPMC K4M and as HPMC K100M polymers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Atorvastatin calcium was obtained as a gift sample from M/s. Caplin point, Pondicherry. HPMC K4M & HPMC K100M was provided by Colorcon Asia Pvt. Ltd. PVP K30 was purchased from Himedia Lab. Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Magnesium stearate was purchased from Loba Chemical Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Lactose, Sodium bicarbonate & Talc were purchased from S.D. Fine chemicals. Citric acid was purchased from Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. All Polymers and excipients used were of pharmaceutical or analytical grade

Preparation of Atorvastatin calcium floating matrix tablets

All the ingredients except magnesium stearate, and talc were blended in glass mortar uniformly. We mixed all the ingredients and passed through the sieve no: 40 and then added Isopropyl Alcohol as a wetting agent to make a coherent mass. The coherent mass was then dried in a hot air oven at a temperature of 45°C for 1 hrs. The dried granules were passed through sieve no: 20 and were lubricated with magnesium stearate and talc, which already passed through the sieve no: 60. The tablets were compressed in a Mega rotary punching machine for

240 mg tablet. The compression force was adjusted to obtaining tablets with hardness in the range of 7-10 kg/cm². The formulations of all the batches were shown in table 1. The tablets were round and flat with an average diameter of 10±0.1 mm and a thickness of 3±0.4 mm

Evaluation of Floating Tablets

The prepared floating tablets were evaluated for Angle of Repose, hardness (Monsanto tester), and friability (Roche type friabilator), drug content, *in vitro* buoyancy and *in vitro* dissolution studies. The results are expressed as mean ± S.D. (n=3).

In vitro buoyancy studies

The *in vitro* buoyancy was determined by floating lag time. The tablets were placed in a 100 ml beaker containing 0.1N hydrochloric acid. The time required for the tablet to rise to the surface and float was determined as floating lag time. The duration of time the dosage form constantly remained on the surface of a medium was determined as the total floating time.

Drug content

Weigh and finely powder 20 tablets. To a quantity of the powdered tablets containing 0.1 g of add 60 ml of 0.1M sodium hydroxide and disperse with the aid of ultrasound for 15 minutes. Add a sufficient quantity of 0.1M sodium hydroxide to produce 100 ml, mix well and filter. To 15 ml of the filtrate adds 50 ml of water and 5.8 ml of 2M hydrochloric acid and sufficient water to produce 100 ml. To 5 ml of the solution add sufficient 0.1M hydrochloric acid to produce 50 ml and mix well. Measure the absorbance of the resulting solution at the maximum at 255 nm, using 0.1M hydrochloric acid in the reference cell.¹¹

Water uptake study

Swelling of the tablet excipients particles involves the absorption of a liquid resulting in an increase in weight and volume. Liquid uptake by the particles may be due to saturation of capillary space

within the particles or hydration of the macromolecule. The liquid enters the particles through pores and bind to large molecule; breaking the hydrogen bond and resulting in the swelling of particle.

The extent of swelling can be measured in the terms of % weight gain by tablet. One tablet was weighted and placed in a containing 200 ml of 0.1N HCl. After each hour, the tablet was removed from a beaker and weighed again upto 5 hrs. The % weight gain by the tablet was calculated by the formula¹²,

$$\text{Swelling Index (S.I)} = \{(W_t - W_o) / W_o\} \times 100$$

Where,

S.I. = swelling index,

W_t = weight of tablet at time t,

W_o = weight of tablet before immersion

In Vitro dissolution studies

In-vitro release studies were carried out using USP XXIII, paddle dissolution test apparatus. 900ml of simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2) was taken in a dissolution vessel and the temperature of the medium was maintained at 37°C±5°C. The speed was 50rpm. 5ml of sample was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals dilute up to 50ml with medium and same volume of a fresh medium was replaced. The samples were analyzed for drug content Against 0.1N HCl as a blank at λ max 255nm using U.V.Spectrophotometer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The floating tablets of Atorvastain calcium were formulated in ten batches F1 to F10. All the formulation was prepared by wet granulation method. The prepared tablets of all the formulations were evaluated for tablet hardness, friability etc. The angle of repose for the formulated blend was carried out. It concludes all the formulations blend was found to be in the range 24.12' to 27.49'. The Thickness for the formulated tablet was carried out. It concludes all the formulated tablet was found to be

in the range 2.650mm to 3.207mm. The % friability was less than 1% in all the formulations ensuring that the tablets were mechanically stable. The drug content for the formulated tablet was carried out. It concludes all the formulated tablet was found to be in the range 96.11% - 98.72% which is within limit as per B.P. 2007 (95-105%).

Buoyancy / Floating test

All the tablets were prepared by the effervescent approach. Sodium bicarbonate was added as a gas-generating agent. Sodium bicarbonate induced carbon dioxide generation in the presence of the dissolution medium (0.1N hydrochloric acid). The combination of sodium bicarbonate and citric acid provided desired floating ability and therefore this combination was selected for the formulation of the floating tablets. The tablet floating lag time (FLT) was found to be minimum 30s and total floating time more than 12h. The floating lag time may be explained as a result of the time required for dissolution medium to penetrate the tablet matrix and develop the swollen layer for entrapment of CO₂ generated in situ. The tablet mass decreased progressively due to liberation of CO₂ and release of drug from the matrix. On the other hand, as solvent front penetrated the glassy polymer layer, the swelling of HPMC K4M and K100M caused an increase in volume of the tablet. The combined effect is a net reduction in density of the tablets, which prolongs the duration of floatation beyond 15h. The pH of the stomach is elevated under the condition (~3.5), therefore citric acid was incorporated in the formulation to provide an acidic medium for sodium bicarbonate; more over citric acid has an stabilizing effect on Atorvastatin calcium formulation. Formulations containing sodium bicarbonate and citric acid in different ratios were studied for their effect on floating lag time of Atorvastatin calcium. It was observed that formulation F1 contains sodium bicarbonate and citric acid in the ratio of 7:1 showed FLT 92S., formulation F2 contains ratio 12:1 showed disintegrate or blast the tablet due to more concentration of gas forming agent and formulation

F3 to F10 contains a ratio of 9:1 showed FLT 30 to 62S.

Water uptake study

The swelling of the polymers used could be determined by water uptake of the tablet. The complete swelling was achieved by the end of 5 hours, so percent swelling was determined at the end of 5 hours for all the developed formulation. The values of swelling index of various batches were evaluated as shown in table 3. There was a significant increase in the percent swelling of the tablet with increase in concentration of polymers. After 5 hours swelling index was observed between 73.49 to 85.24 %.

In vitro dissolution studies

The initial batches [F1-F4], made with HPMC K4M alone showed the complete release in 6 to 9 hrs. Tablets formulated with HPMC K100M alone (F5-F6), too showed a formulation F7 showed a drug release in 12 hrs with 90.63% due to more concentration of HPMC K100M. The formulation [F8 to F10] made with the combination of HPMC K4M & HPMC K100M showed a drug release in 10 to 12 hrs. This was because tablets which are composed of a hydrophilic polymeric matrix, on contact with water build a gel layer around the tablet core which governs the drug release. The drug release from HPMC matrices is controlled for water soluble drug by diffusion and for water insoluble drugs by erosion of outer polymer layer.

Kinetic modelling of drug release

The formulations F1, F3, and F4 showed higher Regression values for first order plot and non-fickian indicating that the drug releases from these formulations were concentration dependent. The formulations F5, F6, F7, F8, F9 and F10 showed higher Regression values for zero order plots and non-fickian indicating that the drug releases from these formulations were concentration independent. The effervescent-based floating drug delivery was a promising approach to achieve *in vitro* buoyancy. The addition of gel-forming polymer HPMC (K4M and K100M) and gas-generating agent sodium bicarbonate along with citric acid was essential to achieve *in vitro* buoyancy. The drug release from the tablets was sufficiently sustained and non-Fickian transport of the drug from tablets was confirmed.

Table No: 1 Formulation of Floating Tablets of Atorvastatin calcium

Ingredients Qty (mg/tab)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Atorvastatin Calcium	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Lactose	106	66	84	74	94	84	74	84	74	64
HPMCK4M	30	40	40	50	—	—	—	10	20	30
HPMC K 100M	—	—	—	—	30	40	50	30	30	30
Sodium bi carbonate	42	72	54	54	54	54	54	54	54	54
Citric acid	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
PVP K 30	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Iso propyl alcohol	qs									
Magnesium stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total weight	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

Table No: 2 Floating Lag Time and Total Floating Time of Atorvastatin Floating tablets

Formulation Code	Floating Lag Time FLT (sec)	Total Floating Time TFT (mins)
F1	92	555
F2	0	0
F3	62	685
F4	51	760
F5	48	670
F6	56	695
F7	55	870
F8	30	665
F9	33	695
F10	35	765

*Formulation F2 tablet was disintegrate or blast after putting in 0.1N HCl, so it's don't have FLT and TFT.

Table No: 3 Swelling Index of Floating Tablet of Atorvastatin calcium.

Time (In Hrs)	Swelling Index (%)								
	F1	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
1	28.23	30.56	34.45	32.82	36.49	32.53	36.64	35.39	34.87
2	39.76	47.18	45.04	47.68	49.57	39.34	46.27	49.45	46.09
3	54.32	56.03	53.61	58.55	60.22	59.66	58.18	65.01	68.33
4	66.07	69.47	68.59	70.71	73.44	76.62	70.12	80.07	79.68
5	76.18	73.49	75.36	77.29	80.06	79.16	83.63	82.44	85.24

Table No: 4 Comparative Cumulative Percentage Drug Release Data for F1 - F10

Time in hrs	F1	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	18.66	14.66	17.61	15.19	10.38	13.78	12.11	12.98	12.02
2	39.09	35.13	34.97	21.35	15.9	23.00	22.38	21.34	19.84
3	65.77	60.95	48.29	35.72	27.27	28.21	30.45	29.31	24.22
4	84.61	79.01	66.13	40.68	39.98	35.9	42.01	33.93	29.08
5	91.8	85.12	75.84	52.56	45.87	41.41	47.06	43.93	34.95
6	96.35	89.69	85.17	67.42	58.99	48.76	55.11	50.62	41.09
7	-	95.84	93.19	72.13	68.18	54.94	63.62	61.25	48.82
8	-	-	96.64	82.83	79.93	61.48	75.66	71.19	57.87
9	-	-	98.2	95.86	90.94	71.04	86.32	79.73	68.41
10	-	-	-	-	92.20	81.68	98.57	86.6	79.39
11	-	-	-	-	98.84	84.27	-	95.27	89.81
12	-	-	-	-	-	90.63	-	-	97.1

Table No: 5 Kinetic Values Obtained from Different Plots of Formulations (F1-F10) of Atorvastatin calcium

Formulation	Zero order plot	First order Plot	Higuchi plot	Korsmeyer Peppas's plot		Possible mechanism of drug release
	Regression Coefficient (R2)	Regression Coefficient (R2)	Regression Coefficient (R2)	Regression Coefficient (R2)	N	
F1	0.956	0.962	0.955	0.972	0.956	First order non fickian
F3	0.934	0.971	0.961	0.951	0.977	First order non fickian
F4	0.944	0.950	0.983	0.979	0.798	First order non fickian Diffusion
F5	0.994	0.845	0.967	0.983	0.862	Zero order non fickian
F6	0.992	0.826	0.977	0.990	1.010	Zero order class 2
F7	0.993	0.917	0.969	0.991	0.764	Zero order non fickian
F8	0.994	0.698	0.961	0.995	0.889	Zero order non fickian
F9	0.996	0.853	0.964	0.990	0.845	Zero order non fickian
F10	0.984	0.759	0.921	0.968	0.846	Zero order non fickian

Figure 1: Swelling Index of Floating Tablets of Atorvastatin calcium (F1 – F10)

Figure 2: Comparative Cumulative Percentage Drug Release Profile for Atorvastation Floating Tablets (F1-F10)

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